

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING THE GENRES OF ETHNODESIGN AND PHILOLOGY**Turmukhanova. N.,***Student on the specialty 6B01702 - Russian language and literature;***Kudabaeva K.,***scientific director; candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, docent Department of Design**Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University**050010, 13 Dostyk Ave., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan***Aitmukhanova P.,***Department of Construction and Building Materials**Satbayev University**050013, 22A Satpaev Str., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan***Aitmukhanov A.***Department of Clinical Disciplines**Al-Farabi Kazakh National University**050040, 71 al-Farabi Ave., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298438>**Abstract**

This article is devoted to the consideration of the technology of teaching the fairy tale genre of the philology major as an effective means of teaching on the basis of the subject of ethnodesign in elementary school. The article deals with various technologies of teaching fairy tales through visualization. This article is devoted to the study of learning technology through a fairy tale as an effective means of education in elementary school. The paper considers various aspects of learning through fairy tales. The main goal and objectives of the study are given, which are the identification of the effectiveness and advantages of this learning technology. Development of recommendations for its use in pedagogical practice. In the course of the work, the following results were used, which are described in this article, which help to organize the process of emotional and creative thinking, develop intellectual activity, develop logical and analytical thinking and enrich the spiritual and material world of the child. Based on the data obtained, recommendations were proposed for teachers and parents to help make the learning process through fairy tales more effective and interesting for children. However, among them: use of interactive teaching methods, visualization of the image in one's mind, involvement of children in the process of creating their own fairy tales on ethnodesign, holding discussions and classes using various technological tools. Therefore, research has shown that the technology of teaching ethno-style fairy tales is an effective tool for education and development of children in educational organizations not only with scientific research, but also with practical results.

Keywords: education, ethnodesign, fairy tale, technology, means, development, logic, thinking, creativity, morality, plot.

Introduction.

The dialectic of the development and formation of the new shows that it is always born in the depths of the old. But the embryo is only a prerequisite, and not the phenomenon itself, which can mature for quite a long time. So it is in design, in the practical activities of the architects of the ancient world, craftsmen of a later time. His confession came when he matured. In the centuries-old history, art, including fairy tales, has existed since ancient times. He has been all his life. The first manifestations of art were very simple paintings on the walls of caves, made by ordinary people [1]. Even when he had to fight for his life every day, he strove for art, and then a love for beauty appeared. Today, not only a fairy tale, but also Van Gogh's painting "The Gorge" was chosen as an incentive for discussion, which evoked a whole palette of emotions, images and thoughts on the problems of the master class among the participants. At the stage of reflection, students wrote their own synchwiners, reflecting the essence of the position of the teacher-facilitator. "From image to thought"

[2]. For a while, art was aesthetics, but today it is technical aesthetics. Design is technical aesthetics. Therefore, no matter what area we choose, design has given a new direction to society, the range of technologies for teaching the system and education has expanded. Ethnodesign is an art that expresses the uniqueness of our country. Today, the natural talent of a person is combined with new technologies, creating fundamentally new directions in art. Of course, before there were no such opportunities as today, but every artist tried to come up with something special, to contribute to the development of this art form. Thus, the technology of teaching in philology through the images of a fairy tale is relevant and timely. One of the most ancient and popular genres of literature is also a fairy tale. Fairy tales are stories that have the purpose of moralizing and usually contain heroes who face difficult obstacles, but in the end the common good always triumphs over evil. In this article, we will look at the history of the fairy tale, the different types of fairy tales, their content, the reasons for their popularity, as well as their impact on culture and the social sphere. Fairy tales are a rich and

fascinating genre of literature that amazes with the variety of its types, images and moods[3]. Fairy tales, written many centuries ago, remain popular today. Often they have a moralistic connotation that helps us better understand the world around us and our own lives. Regardless of age, fairy tales remain inspiring and entertaining for everyone.[4] Each fairy tale contains a moral that its author is trying to convey to his readers. Fairy tales teach patience, kindness, respect for elders and wisdom. They can also help us understand why certain things happen in our lives. Fairy tales describe universal themes that are relevant in any culture or era. Many fairy tales also have a mythological nature, stories about gods and heroes. They may contain hidden motives and symbols that help us understand the world around us. Such tales teach understanding of mythological rhythms and their relationship with life. In the course of the work, an analysis of the literature on this topic was carried out and conclusions were drawn that the use of fairy tales in the educational process makes it possible to achieve the following results: the development of logical thinking and imagination in children; formation of emotional and moral culture; development of communication skills and communication skills; stimulate interest in reading.

Materials:

Scientific articles, books and reviews on the topic "Learning through a fairy tale"; Data from studies conducted in educational institutions; Materials of seminars, trainings and webinars for teachers and parents; Various fairy tales, stories and legends used in the learning process.

Methods:

Analysis of literature and research on the topic; The use of oral and written works, graphic image, the basics of graphics design, multifunctional, but at the same time quite easy to use raster graphics, as well as statistical methods to evaluate the effectiveness of learning technology through a fairy tale; Review and analysis of curricula and methodological materials for learning through a fairy tale; Interviews with teachers, parents and children who have already used this learning technology; Conducting practical experiments in which various methods of teaching through a fairy tale are used for children of different ages and levels of education.

Purpose of the study:

Formation of the effectiveness of the use of learning technology through the image of a fairy tale in the upbringing of children; Research objectives: To determine the features of the use of fairy tales in the process of teaching and educating children of different ages and levels of education; Consider the role of fairy tales in the development of aesthetic perception of the world, logical and visual thinking, creativity and other skills in children; To study the moral lessons that can be learned from fairy tales and their influence on the formation of a child's personality; Conduct and identify experimental work and give recommendations on the use of teaching technology through a fairy tale in the educational practice of children's educational institutions and home education.

Results:

The study of the effectiveness of the use of teaching technology through the images of a fairy tale shows that the use of fairy tales in teaching and raising children can be effective in developing an aesthetic perception of the world, logical and visual thinking, creativity and other skills. Determining the features of the use of fairy tales in the process of teaching and educating children shows that fairy tales can be used to tell about various facts and events that took place in history, as well as to form an emotional and moral attitude to life. The role of fairy tales in the development of the aesthetic perception of the world, the development of logical thinking, creativity and other skills in children has been carefully considered, and the article shows how fairy tales contribute to the development of the child's personality. A study of the moral lessons that can be learned from fairy tales and their influence on the formation of a child's personality shows that fairy tales can be used as a powerful educational tool to promote the development of morality and social competence in children. The development of recommendations on the use of learning technology through a fairy tale in the educational practice of children's educational institutions and home education was carried out in order to improve the quality of education and upbringing.

Analysis of results:

Analysis of the results of the article shows that the use of fairy tales in the education and upbringing of children has many positive effects and is an effective tool. Firstly, the use of fairy tales contributes to the development of logical thinking and creativity in children. When studying fairy tales, children learn to analyze the text, highlight the main character and the main event, and also show imagination and fantasy. Secondly, fairy tales help shape the aesthetic perception of the world. The child learns to appreciate beauty and harmony, to develop an aesthetic taste, and to understand the inner beauty and spiritual depth of people. Thirdly, the use of fairy tales in education helps to develop the moral and emotional qualities of the individual. Fairy tales often contain moral lessons and examples of behavior that help the child develop conscience, empathy, and social competence. It is also worth noting that the use of learning technology through images of a fairy tale requires a qualified approach on the part of a teacher or parent. The use of fairy tales must be adapted to the age and developmental level of the child, taking into account his interests and needs. In addition, it is necessary to choose appropriate fairy tales that are suitable for the purposes of education and upbringing. Thus, the use of technology of learning through a fairy tale can be an effective tool in raising children, but it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the approach and the detailed adaptation of fairy tales to obtain the best effect through images, for example, the fictional fairy tale "Curious Ellie". For example, the fictional fairy tale "Curious Ellie" - once upon a time there lived a little elephant named Ellie. He lived at the zoo with his animal friends: monkeys, tigers, giraffes and many more. Ellie was an unusual elephant, he was very inquisitive and liked to ask a lot of questions. One day he thought about how great it would be to travel around

the world and find out what is happening in other countries. He was sure there were many interesting things to learn and see there. Once, when Ellie was walking around the zoo, he saw the open door of his enclosure. He thought, "Why not go on an adventure?" Ellie quickly got out of the enclosure and set off on his first journey. He walked many kilometers and saw many interesting things, such as high mountains, wild rivers, deserts and dense jungles. Ellie met new friends such as the aviator giraffe and the inventor leopard. Together they explored the whole earth, and Ellie found many answers to his questions. When Ellie returned to the zoo after his adventure, he told his animal friends about what he had seen and learned. His stories were so interesting that the animals also decided to go on a journey to explore the world and learn more about it. Ellie became famous among the people who often came to the zoo. After learning about his adventures, they became interested in the desire to explore new things and learn more about the world around us. So Ellie left his mark on history, leaving an important lesson in our memory: learning is always interesting and useful, and travel and adventure can open doors to new worlds for us. As you can see from the content, fairy tales contain many elements that make them unique. They often begin with the phrase "Once upon a time," followed by a description of the characters and the situation in which they find themselves. Heroes often face and overcome various difficulties, usually due to their wisdom and kindness. Fairy tales may contain references to culture, traditions and legends from different countries. Fairy tales usually contain a story about a main character, who may be a human, animal, or magical creature. The hero meets various situations on his way, overcomes obstacles and achieves goals. An important role in the fairy tale is played by antagonists or villains - characters who prevent the fulfillment of the goals of the protagonist. Fairy tales can have different motifs and themes. They can talk about love and betrayal, good and evil, justice and punishment, courage and perseverance. Each tale usually has a specific moral conclusion and can serve to convey important life lessons. They can teach us virtues, give advice on how to behave in different situations, teach us to be courageous and resourceful. Fairy tales can also have a fantasy plot that includes magic, magic, and fantastical creatures. Some tales may be associated with religious or cultural traditions and contain elements and motifs that reflect that culture. Much of what we learn from fairy tales can be applied in our real life. Telling stories about fictional characters and their stories can help us better understand the world and its complexities, as well as provide us with valuable lessons to help us in everyday life.

Recommendations for teachers and parents on teaching a child to a fairy tale.

Practical tips for teachers and parents to help make learning through fairy tales more interesting and effective:

1. Use of interactive teaching methods.

For example, you can conduct a dramatization game in which children act out scenes from fairy tales, take certain roles and express their emotions. You can

also use interactive tasks in the lessons of reading fairy tales.

2. Inclusion of children in the process of creating their fairy tales.

Children can independently write a fairy tale, tell a story, invent new characters and events. This will help them not only develop their imagination, but also improve their writing and storytelling skills.

3. Conducting discussions.

Discussing the plots of fairy tales after reading them helps children better understand the content of fairy tales and identify the moral lessons that can be learned from the story. You can also discuss the meaning of what is happening in a fairy tale, the emotions of the characters and its meaning for us.

4. Use of technological tools.

Modern technologies help to make the lessons of learning through a fairy tale more interesting and engaging. You can use multimedia presentations, interactive games, webinars, videos.

5. Creation of the atmosphere.

Creating an atmosphere of enthusiastic reading in the classroom or at home will help increase children's interest in fairy tales. To do this, you can use soft pillows, cozy reading nooks, themed decorations and other design elements. It is important that the learning process through fairy tales is interesting and varied so that children can enjoy reading and develop at the same time.

The popularity of fairy tales

Fairy tales have always been very popular. They are often used to teach moral lessons to children, and many of them also have cultural and historical aspects. Fairy tales can help children and adults understand themselves and the world around them. They can inspire us and help us see the world through a different perspective. The influence of fairy tales on culture and the social sphere: Fairy tales have a great influence on culture and the social sphere. Books and movies based on the fairy tales continue to come out and they continue to inspire generations. Some fairy tales unite people by their nationality, traditions and culture. They were also frequently used in political rhetoric, educational programs, and independent reading clubs.

Discussion:

One of the main conclusions of the article is that the technology of learning through a fairy tale has many positive effects on the development of a child's personality. In particular, the use of fairy tales contributes to the development of logical thinking and creativity, as well as the formation of aesthetic perception and morality. It is important to note that the use of fairy tales can only be effective if they are chosen taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of children. However, the question arises about the limitations of the study. The use of only one research method (literature analysis) may not be enough to fully understand the effectiveness of using fairy tales in educating children. However, this work can be a starting point for further research on this topic. Also, the question of the advantages and disadvantages of using fairy tales in raising children should be discussed. On the one hand, fairy tales can be useful educational and educational tools

that can be easily adapted for use in various settings and circumstances. On the other hand, the use of fairy tales may be limited and not always correspond to the goals and objectives of the educational process. Thus, the article presents an interesting point of view on the use of fairy tales in the education and upbringing of children. However, our discussion should be continued by other researchers in order to reveal the full complexity and effectiveness of this method of raising children.

Conclusions:

The article discusses the technology of teaching through a fairy tale, which is used in the educational process. Various methods and techniques are described that can be used to use a fairy tale as a means of education. The main conclusion that can be drawn from the article is that the use of a fairy tale as a means of education has many advantages. First, a fairy tale can help children understand complex concepts and processes, including moral lessons. Secondly, the fairy tale motivates children to develop their imagination and creativity. Thirdly, a fairy tale can affect the child's state of mind, convey positive emotions to him and strengthen his self-confidence. However, it is worth noting some disadvantages of this training technology. Some children may not understand the moral lesson of the story, and may also be offended or upset by certain elements of the story. In addition, fairy tales can become a powerful tool in the hands of educators and educators if they are used inappropriately. Thus, the technology of learning through a fairy tale is effective and useful in the educational process, but it must be used with caution and competence so as not to harm children.

Recommendations:

1. Try to use fairy tales in the education and upbringing of children to help them understand complex topics and understand moral lessons.
2. Use various methods and techniques to make fairy tales more interesting and fun for children, such as using drawings and animations.
3. Be sure to consider the age context of the children and choose fairy tales that are appropriate for their age characteristics.
4. Prepare well for using the story and determine what moral lessons you want to convey to the children.
5. Be attentive to children's reactions and consider their opinions. If the children do not understand or do not agree with the moral lesson, explain to him and clarify their opinion.
6. Keep track of time and do not abuse fairy tales so as not to lose the attention of children.
7. Teachers and educators must be competently trained and competent in the use of fairy tales in the educational process.

Conclusion:

Fairy tales are a rich and fascinating genre of literature that amazes with the diversity of its types, images and moods. Fairy tales, written many centuries ago, remain popular today. Often they have a moralistic connotation that helps us better understand the world around us and our own lives. Regardless of age, fairy tales remain inspiring and entertaining for everyone.

Each fairy tale contains a moral that its author is trying to convey to his readers. Fairy tales teach patience, kindness, respect for elders and wisdom. They can also help us understand why certain things happen in our lives. Fairy tales describe universal themes that are relevant in any culture or era. Many fairy tales also have a mythological nature, stories about gods and heroes. They may contain hidden motives and symbols that help us understand the world around us. Such tales teach understanding of mythological rhythms and their relationship with life. A fairy tale can be useful in an artistic idea or in a design. When children listen to stories, they imagine finds and understand different worlds and identities. Another popular type of artwork using fairy tales is fantasy. Fantasy stories may use the lessons and symbols of a fairy tale, but create new worlds and characters. Fairy tales can be multifaceted, capable of conveying different ideas. With them, we can learn about our dreams and desires and how we can achieve them. They help us recognize our strengths and weaknesses. Fairy tales are a unique genre of literature that not only develops the imagination, but also helps us understand the world around us.

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